

The Frequency of Anxiety and Depression in Patients with Hepatitis C at a Public Sector Liver Centre in Pakistan

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Abstract

Background: Co-morbid anxiety and depression are associated with hepatitis C. Co-morbid depression is associated with increased medical symptom burden, poor quality of life and poor adherence to self-care regimens. However, in Pakistan, the data assessing the psychiatric aspect of Hepatitis C is limited.

Objective: The objective of this study was to evaluate the frequency of anxiety and depression in patients with Hepatitis C at a public sector liver centre in Pakistan.

Methods: Participants who were positive for hepatitis C were selected by non-probability convenience sampling. Informed consent was taken verbally and a questionnaire-based interview was implied. The questionnaire scored anxiety and depression on a verified Urdu translated version of Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS). Data was analysed with SPSS v. 22.

Results: Out of 146 participants 40% were males and 60% were females with an average age of 47.2 years. Anxiety and depression were present in 47.9% and 41.8% patients of hepatitis C respectively. There was a significant association of drug use with anxiety ($p=0.01$) and depression ($p=0.03$). Urban residency was significantly associated with anxiety ($p=0.04$). On comparing means it was found that women had a higher average anxiety score compared to the males (10.2 ± 4.6 vs. 9.5 ± 4.6) while males had a higher average depression score compared with females (9.8 ± 4.3 vs. 9.3 ± 4.5). However, the correlation between gender and HADS scores was not significant.

Conclusion: There is a high frequency of anxiety and depression among hepatitis C patients thus regular psychiatric screening, referral, treatment and follow-up is recommended.

Key Words: Anxiety, Depression, Hepatitis C, Hospital Anxiety, Depression Scale

Introduction

It is estimated that 130 million people are affected by chronic hepatitis C infection worldwide¹. The prevalence is as high as 16%, in some areas of Pakistan². Increased medical symptoms, functional disability, medical costs, poor adherence, and increased risk of morbidity and mortality in patients with chronic medical disorders is associated with co-morbid depression³. According to WHO, it is the third main cause of disability-adjusted life year (DALY)⁴. Depression, being a major cause of disability; is predicted to be the second cause of disability in adults⁵.

An Irish study shows 24% frequency of anxiety disorder and 28% frequency of depressive disorders among Hepatitis C patients⁶. Chinese studies report the rate of psychiatric complaints in patients with chronic liver disease as 38.1%-51.1% while a similar study in Pakistan showed a much higher frequency of depression and anxiety i.e. 71.6% and 70.6% respectively⁷⁻⁹. WHO estimates that in Pakistan the percentage of population having anxiety is 3.5% while that of depression is 4.2%¹⁰. The number of people with co-morbid HCV and depressive disorder (including minor depression) increased significantly between 1995 and 2005 from 18% to over 35% of all people with diagnosed HCV¹¹.

The above-mentioned statistics indicate that high prevalence, chronicity, complications and cirrhosis are not the only problems of Hepatitis C. The disease has a psychiatric aspect as well. Lack of education and awareness about anxiety and depression leaves this aspect of illness unaddressed. Furthermore, lack of existing medical literature in this field, especially in developing countries makes it the need of the hour to channelize research work in this direction. This study will not only quantify the existing problem in our set-up but will also provide foundations for further studies that will throw light upon this issue.

Patients and Methods

The descriptive cross-sectional study, with a 10 months duration, was conducted at a public sector Liver Centre, at Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi. Patients who were anti HCV antibody and/or HCV RNA positive for more than 6 months were included; while those who had positive past and/or family history of depression and anxiety, any other co-existing cause of cirrhosis (e.g. hepatitis B, primary biliary cirrhosis), other severe chronic diseases (e.g. COPD, cancer, heart failure or Ischemic heart disease), HIV positive or those on interferon treatment were excluded from the study. Non-probability convenience sampling technique was applied. Verbal consent was taken from subjects prior to being interviewed via questionnaire. The study was approved by ethical review board of Rawalpindi Medical University.

Social, demographic and psychological data was collected using a questionnaire based on a validated Urdu translated version of hospital anxiety and depression scale (HADS); proven by studies to be reliable¹²⁻¹⁴. Socio-demographics included age, gender, marital status, drug use and address. Disease related data included means of diagnosis, treatment details and current status. Symptoms of anxiety and depression were scored using HADS and the scores were then classified as normal, borderline or cases.

The methods of descriptive and analytical statistics were applied. The data was analysed via SPSS version 22. The categorical variables were presented as percentages. Categorical data comparisons were performed using the χ^2 and any p value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included 160 participants out of which 14 did not satisfy the inclusion/exclusion criteria. Of the remaining 146 participants, 58 (40%) were males and 88 (60%) were females with an average age of 47.2 years. On assessing the frequency of anxiety, 47.9% were cases, 20.5% were borderline and 31.5% were normal; while assessing depression 41.8% were cases, 25.3% were borderline and 32.9% were normal. The presence of anxiety and depression relative to the selected socio-demographic parameters is presented in Table I and Table II respectively. There was a significant association of drug use with anxiety (p=0.01) and depression (p=0.03). Urban residency was significantly associated with anxiety (p=0.04), however, there was no significant association with depression. The correlation of HAD scale score with

social and demographic parameters was studied by Pearson correlation and it did not show any other significant correlation.

The frequency of cases of anxiety was higher in females compared with males (64.77% vs. 22.4%). The frequency is also higher in females for depression (46.59% vs. 34.48%). On comparing means it was found that women had a higher average anxiety score compared to the males (10.2 ± 4.6 vs. 9.5 ± 4.6). On the contrary, males had a higher average depression score compared to the females (9.8 ± 4.3 vs. 9.3 ± 4.5). However, the association gender with HADS scores was not significant.

Social and demographic parameters		Normal	Border-line	Case	P-value
Gender (%)	Males	34 (58.6%)	11 (19.0%)	13 (22.4%)	0.49
	Females	12 (13.6%)	19 (21.5%)	57 (64.8%)	
Age (%)	Below 50	28 (34.6%)	17 (21.0%)	36 (44.4%)	0.84
	Equal to or above 50	18 (27.7%)	13 (20.0%)	34 (52.3%)	
Marital status (%)	Single	6 (35.3%)	3 (17.6%)	8 (47.1%)	0.14
	Married	40 (31.0%)	27 (20.9%)	62 (48.1%)	
Drug use (%)	User	6 (35.3%)	3 (17.6%)	8 (47.1%)	0.01
	Non-user	40 (31.0%)	27 (20.9%)	62 (48.1%)	
Residency (%)	Urban	30 (30.0%)	21 (21.0%)	49 (49.0%)	0.04
	Rural	16 (34.8%)	9 (19.6%)	21 (45.6%)	

Table I: Anxiety relative to social and demographic parameters

Discussion

The critical finding of this study is the high frequency of anxiety (47.9%) and depression (41.8%). A previous study in Pakistan has reported a frequency of 70.6% and 71.6% of anxiety and depression respectively¹⁵. Likewise, another study in Pakistan described that 59.4% patients with hepatitis C had depression¹⁶.

Social and demographic parameters		Normal	Border line	Case	P-value
Gender (%)	Males	25 (43.1%)	13 (22.4%)	20 (34.5%)	0.17
	Females	23 (26.1%)	24 (27.3%)	41 (46.6%)	
Age (%)	Below 50	34 (42.0%)	17 (21.0%)	30 (37.0%)	0.18
	Equal to or above 50	14 (21.5%)	20 (30.8%)	31 (47.7%)	
Marital status (%)	Single	8 (66.7%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (33.3%)	0.15
	Married	40 (29.8%)	37 (27.6%)	57 (42.5%)	
Drug use (%)	User	7 (41.2%)	3 (17.6%)	7 (41.2%)	0.03
	Non-user	41 (31.8%)	34 (26.4%)	54 (41.9%)	
Residency (%)	Urban	29 (29.0%)	26 (26.0%)	45 (45.0%)	0.11
	Rural	19 (41.3%)	11 (23.9%)	16 (34.8%)	

Table II: Depression relative to social and demographic parameters

In an Irish study, the frequency of anxiety and depression are 24% and 28% respectively⁶ whereas; in England, 18% screened positive for anxiety or depression¹⁷. Australian studies have reported anxiety ranging between 41 to 44% and depression ranging from 27 to 34%^{18,19}. A study from Serbia outlined depression up to 62.9 %²⁰. There are higher frequencies of anxiety and depression among under-developed countries like Pakistan and Serbia, owing to lack of awareness, availability of psychiatric health care and lack of resources.

In our study we found that there was a significant association of drug use with anxiety and depression this is in accord with previous studies that demonstrate association of alcohol and drug use with mood disorders and anxiety disorder^{21,22}. Our study did not show any significant correlation of HADS scores with age; in concurrence with a past study²³. On the contrary, other studies have shown increased rates of anxiety and depression with increasing age of the patient¹⁷⁻²⁰. In our study there is higher frequency of

cases among females compared with males which is in accord with previous studies⁴. However, in our study the mean score of anxiety is higher in females while that of depression being higher in males.

This study did not focus on the somatic complaints of chronic liver disease. However, other studies indicate that co-existing anxiety and depression are associated with increased somatic complaints, anger and stigma²⁴⁻²⁶. Studies also imply that anger and stigma are associated with hepatitis C²⁷. It is implicated that severity of depression correlates proportionately with quality of life^{13,25}. Some studies show that hepatitis C is more likely to be associated with psychiatric disorders compared with hepatitis B and other chronic liver diseases^{28,29}.

The study employed HAD scale for detecting anxiety and depression. The use of this scale limits the diagnosis to a probable diagnosis instead of a definite diagnosis. Moreover, as the study employed non probability sampling and setting was a specialized liver centre the findings cannot be generalized to the hepatitis C population not in contact with medical care.

Conclusion

There is high frequency of anxiety and depression among Hepatitis C patients. It becomes imperative for health care professionals to be adequately equipped to diagnose the psychiatric aspects of Hepatitis C and to deal with it accordingly. Regular screening, subsequent referral for mental health treatment and follow-up in Hepatitis C patients is recommended. Moreover, public healthcare psychiatric institutes need to be expanded to allow specialists to refer patients.

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Authors Contributions

Mujtaba Haider Bukhari: Paper writing, data analysis, data collection, **Ahsan Tariq:** Data collection, interpretation, data analysis, **Muhammad Sumeed Khalid:** Data collection, interpretation and analysis, **Ali Sufyan:** Literature Review

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